

Applying Attributes to Improve Human Activity Recognition

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Abstract

Activity and event recognition from video has utilized low-level features over higher-level text-based class attributes and ontologies because they traditionally have been more effective on small datasets. However, by including human knowledge-driven associations between actions and attributes while recognizing the lower-level attributes with their temporal relationships, we can learn a much greater set of activities as well as improve low-level feature-based algorithms by incorporating an expert knowledge ontology.

In an event ontology, events can be broken down into actions, and these can be decomposed further into attributes. For example, throwing events can include throwing of stones or baseballs with the object being relocated from a hand through the air to a location of interest. The throwing can be broken down into the many physical attributes that can be used to describe the motion like $BodyPartsUsed = Hands$, $BodyPartArticulation-Arm = OneArmRaisedOverHead$, and many others. Building general attributes from video and merging them into an ontology for recognition allows significant reuse for the development of activity and event classifiers. Each activity or event classifier is composed of interacting attributes the same way sentences are composed of interacting letters to create a complete language.

1. Introduction

Action recognition has utilized low-level features over higher-level class attributes and ontologies because they traditionally have been more effective. In fact, at a recent Action Classification Challenge at the 2013 international conference on computer vision (ICCV) there were no contestants who used the compiled class attributes, and the top six contestants used only low-level attributes [1]. However, an approach with class-based attributes may

improve the accuracy of methods when traditional low-level features do not perform as well as expected.

One of the cases when low-level attributes do not work well is when the data is mislabeled or corrupted in some way. The worst case is mislabeling, where the classifier is trained on the wrong data. Given enough accurate data, mislabeling of a few cases is not a severe handicap, but on smaller datasets it can make a significant difference. We isolated one action dataset that had been of particular trouble for low-level approaches, the Action Set 2 from the MSR-Action3D dataset [2] which has eight action classes with sixty instances of each class. The dataset is compiled using a time-of-flight depth sensor to capture the human actions. The 3-D depth maps are skeletonized to reduce the dimensionality of the data. This skeletonization procedure has some failures and some mistakes. However, the skeletons readily provide ontologically significant action attributes, such as 'Body Part Articulation-Arm = One_Arm_Motion' which can be used to validate the skeletonization.

Instead of learning an attribute ontology from the data, we apply a knowledge-based approach and utilize a previously developed model of the attributes and skeletal relationships for particular activities. However, we needed to extend the model to characterize the particular activities in the dataset. In order to apply a previously developed human action ontology to the skeletonized actions, we utilized and extended the action attributes compiled for the Action Classification Challenge [1] to fit the different actions in the MSR-Action3D dataset [2]. An excerpt of some of the attributes for a punching action is shown in Table 1.

By applying the attribute ontology to the training set, we could prevent inaccurate, inconsistent, damaged, or mislabeled cases from damaging the classifier without reducing the richness of the features. There is the risk of that an excessively strict ontology would dramatically reduce the size of the training set and result in performance degradation, so a preliminary classification should be performed and the effect of applying knowledge-based

ontological restrictions to the training set can be tested and the final result calculated on an evaluation dataset. A subset of the action attribute ontology is shown in Table 1. Using the knowledge-based ontology, we could identify skeletonization mistakes that made certain cases ontologically inconsistent.

The next section discusses related work on action recognition and the application of ontologies to action recognition. Section 3 describes the dataset. Section 4 describes the ontology, while section 5 describes the classifier that is improved using a knowledge-based ontology. Section 6 tabulates the results and Section 7 contains the conclusions.

Table 1. A subset of the action attributes that are present or absent in the action ‘Punch’

Action Attributes	Punch
Body Part Articulation-Arm = One_Arm_Motion	1
Body Part Articulation-Arm = Two_Arms_Motion	1
Body Part Articulation-Head = Facing_Up	0
Body Part Articulation-Head = Facing_Front	1
Body Part Articulation-Head = Facing_Sideways	1
Body Part Articulation-Head = Straight_Position	1
Body Part Articulation-Head = Tilted_Position	1
Body Part Articulation-Feet = Touching_Ground	1
Body Part Articulation-Feet = In_Air	0

2. Related Work

Human activity recognition has already been explored using images and video. Activity recognition techniques can be grouped into data-driven [3] and knowledge-driven [4] approaches. Data-driven techniques use machine learning approaches to discern an activity from the training data. Space-time methods such as space-time volumes, spatio-temporal features, and trajectories have been successful. For classification, generic approaches like support vector machines and hidden Markov models have done well.

Space-time approaches treat video as spatial (x,y) and temporal (t) axes [5-10]. An action can be described as a 3D shape in space-time and compared to labeled actions [11,12] with extensions [5-7]. For video, the spatial dimensions are x and y. By including the z value from depth images, reasonable recognition can be achieved [9]. Improvement can be achieved in recognition accuracy by including the third spatial dimension [6]. An action graph approach on a bag-of-3D-points can encode actions and produce an improvement in recognition accuracy [10]. Random occupancy patterns (ROP) from the 4D video

volume were tested on MSR-Action3D dataset, and achieved 86.2% accuracy [13]. Three-dimensional joint positions were used to develop a view-invariant posture representation [14]. Combining features from RGB images, depth maps, and skeleton joints to recognize human activities has also been done [15].

HMMs are often applied for classification of activities with real-time performance. Body joints can be obtained [16] and the temporal patterns of the joint feature vectors were tested on the MSR-Action3D dataset [2], achieving 88.2% recognition accuracy [17] across all classes. Naïve-Bayes-Nearest-Neighbor was also used to achieve similar accuracy, [18] demonstrating that many classifiers would work given a thoughtful choice of features. The same work observed that the actionlet mining method was effective to handle noise and errors in skeleton joint positions. Recurrent neural networks [19], dynamic temporal warping [20], and hidden Markov models have also been used [21].

An action ontology provides a description of the activity using well-structured terminology with a number of properties that are measureable. A well-built ontology could be used, understood, and shared between humans and computers [22-24]. A human action ontology was developed [1] that was used and extended for this work.

3. Dataset

The MSR-Action3D dataset [2] is a benchmark dataset for 3D action recognition that provides sequences of depth maps and skeleton joints. It includes 20 actions performed by 10 subjects performing each action 3 times. An example is shown in Figure 1 for “high wave”, where the motion of the arms, legs, head, and torso are shown with the depth dimension removed.

Figure 1: Example action of “high wave” from the MSR-Action3D dataset.

The activities in this dataset are defined by pose, such as “forward punch” and “side boxing” defined to be separate classes of “punch” as well as “forward kick” and “side kick” which are only defined in the reference frame of the individual’s pose. Since the activities are defined in pose-relative terminology, the data to utilize should be extractable in the subject’s pose reference frame. Some of the actions in this dataset are listed in Table 2.

4. Ontology and Attributes for Actions

An ontology for action recognition [1] was evaluated for the smaller set of actions Action Set 2 of the MSR-Action3D dataset [2]. Attributes that were useful in separating classes were used, like 'Body Part Articulation-Arm = Two Arms Motion' which only is in the majority of 'Two Hand Wave' cases. We also extended the ontology to include 'Body Part Articulation-Arm = One Arm Raised Head Level' and 'Body Part Articulation-Arm = One Arm Extend Side' to help evaluate the 'Side Boxing' and 'High Wave' classes.

Table 2. Two subsets of actions used for the MSR-Action3D dataset

Action set 1 (AS1)	Action set 2 (AS2)
Horizontal wave (2)	High wave (1)
Hammer (3)	Hand catch (4)
Forward punch (5)	Draw x (7)
High throw (6)	Draw circle (9)
Hand clap (10)	Two hand wave (11)
Bend (13)	Forward kick (14)
Tennis serve (18)	Side boxing (12)
Pickup throw (20)	Draw tick (8)

The implementation of heuristics to test for ontological aberrations in the training data was simplified by utilizing the extracted skeletal joints. For example, testing for the percentage of time that the 'Body Part Articulation-Arm = One Arm Raised Head Level' was a simple measurement of whether the location of the hand was above the location of the neck. We found that the MSR-Action3D dataset is well-suited for developing quick measures of attributes and then applying ontological reasoning.

5. Classification Approach

The 3D joint velocities are used to recognize the motion of the human body. Our key observation is that representing the human movement as joint velocities results in effective features that can be represented in the pose reference frame and which are invariant under time dilation. In other words, motions done more slowly or quickly can be robustly compared by time-dilating the extracted velocities using Dynamic Time Warping [25]. In some sense, the actions can be stretched in the time domain to compare to other actions.

For this work, 20 joint positions are tracked using a skeleton tracker [16] and compiled into a time series of joints i depicted as $\mathbf{p}_i(t) = (x_i(t); y_i(t); z_i(t))$ at a frame t . The coordinates are then normalized to reduce dependencies on height, initial body orientation and location.

For each joint i , we extract the normalized pose-referenced velocity features by taking the difference between the position of joint $i(t)$ and that of joint $i(t-1)$ and dividing by the time step dt . The resulting velocity vector is:

$$\mathbf{v}_i(t) = ((x_i(t) - x_i(t-1))/dt; (y_i(t) - y_i(t-1))/dt; (z_i(t) - z_i(t-1))/dt) \quad (1)$$

for each joint i in the skeletonized action. Note that the normalization has left the extracted velocities in the initial pose reference frame of the subject, which means that the extracted velocities should be able to distinguish pose-defined activities. The actions can be visualized by looking at the velocities over time.

To classify a signature, the joint-velocity heatmap is combined with attribute heatmaps and compared to a known database of joint-velocity heatmaps. The comparison utilizes a Dynamic Time Warping [25] of the joint-velocity heatmaps as a distance function between signatures. A large measured distance between signals is a measure of the difference between signals, while a small measured distance is indicative of the similarity of two signals. The combination of attributes and measured velocities was balanced by using a weight between the two measurements. A large weight favored the measured velocities while a small weight favored the attributes.

We did not try to pick out the most relevant features using PCA as had been done in other work [26] though this may be done in future work for comparison. Since the other work kept 85% of the eigenvalues, the dimensionality reduction is not great, and the eigenvectors may be less intuitive than the original skeletal joint velocities.

We did not use the attributes to remove poor training cases as had been done previously [27] since the attributes should perform the same or better than that approach.

6. Experimental Results

Several initial experiments were run on the MSR-Action3D dataset various weights between the attribute measurements and the joint velocity measurements. The initial results are shown in a series of confusion matrices in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Performance of the classifier with different weights measured on the MSR-Action3D dataset.

The refinement using attributes does redistribute misclassifications and improve the classifier, but the

attributes by themselves are not a strong classifier. This can be seen when the relative weighting emphasizes the attributes and becomes small, the performance degrades. The best performance was achieved with a weight that balanced the velocities and the attributes.

7. Conclusions

This work has shown that recognition of human actions can be improved using attributes to add additional information into the classifier. By incorporating human knowledge about action attributes and balancing it with the measured low-level features, the classifier can achieve an improved performance.

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